

The Influence of Operation Performance, Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty of Central Java KRL (Solo - Yogyakarta) in 2022

Awang Kurniawan
The Transportation of Management
Trisakti Institute of Transportation & Logistics
DKI Jakarta, Indonesia

Ir. Soemino Eko Saputro, MM., IPU., ASEAN Eng.
The Transportation of Management
Trisakti Institute of Transportation & Logistics
DKI Jakarta, Indonesia

Dr. Francis Tantri, SE., MM.
The Transportation of Management
Trisakti Institute of Transportation & Logistics
DKI Jakarta, Indonesia

Dr. Olfabri, S. Sos., MM.
The Transportation of Management
Trisakti Institute of Transportation & Logistics
DKI Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- The influence of operational performance also service quality which is bring customer satisfaction are determining factors to make a customer loyalty. Hence, there are some necessary efforts that have to be done to increase the customer satisfaction who uses KRL (Solo-Yogyakarta). This research was conducted in Central Java KRL stations with a sample size of about 80 passengers. All the data was gathered by some form of instrument with Scale Likert. The method of analysis of the data used analytics the path analysis. In the analys, we find that operational performance significantly having positive correlation - customer satisfaction and so are the quality of services on customer satisfaction. There for, relevant operational performance and service quality in customer satisfaction have contributed to increasing customer loyalty, and thus intervening variables such as customer satisfaction, have a major role in improving of operational performance and the service quality is towards customer loyalty.

Keywords:- Operation Performance, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, & Loyalty Customer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Central Java KRL (Solo – Yogyakarta) operated by PT Kereta Comuter Indonesia as part of PT KAI (Persero) which as a state-owned company engaged in public services must refer to A guide from governmental regulations number 65 of 2005 concerning Guidelines for the Preparation and Determination of Minimum Service Standards and Decree of the Minister of Administrative Reform Number 63 of 2003 concerning General Guidelines for the Implementation of Public Services which explains that government agencies are

required to carry out The community satisfaction index to assess the success of service delivery has done. The Ministry of Administrative Reform has also established General guidelines drafting the society's satisfaction index through Menpan Decree No. 25 of 2004, which explains the definition of the public A community satisfaction index hpi " is the data and information about the level of community satisfaction obtained from the measurement result quantitatively and qualitatively over public opinion in gaining the services of a public service by comparing between hope and needs". In particular, the Ministry of Transportation itself has stipulated Minister of Transportation Regulation No. 69 of 2019 which explains the Minimum Service Standards for Railway Transport of the Peoples as a guideline for providing the necessary facilities in transporting people by train.

However, during the operation of the Central Java (Solo - Yogyakarta) KRL, the current problems are, including the lack of even availability of stations, which means that people are still thinking about traveling using KRL, the long arrival time of KRL and the number of KRL fleets is not large, there are still delays. the arrival time of the KRL and the long stopping time for the KRL to be able to depart again at the station, this will have an impact on working users and will reduce public confidence, not to mention the inadequate facilities at the station where what users are looking for is comfort at the station either while waiting for the arrival of the KRL or others, then accessibility with other modes of transportation which is not easy or even not yet available where users, whether getting off or going up, will use other modes of transportation either to get to the station or after leaving the station, and in addition operational coordination is still not good. As well as employees or officers who feel

that they have not mastered the company's service products well, which means that the information conveyed does not reach customers and does not meet the expectations desired by customers or the service user community, which results in feelings of disappointment received by KRL users and impact on the good name of PT. KCI, which according to the explanation above, will have an impact on the loyalty of Solo – Yogyakarta Electric Rail Train (KRL) users.

➤ *Research Problems*

This study tries to answer the following questions:

- Is there the direct effect of operational performance on customer satisfaction for KRL Central Java (Solo – Yogyakarta) in 2022?
- Is there the direct effect of the quality of services in central java (Solo – Yogyakarta) KRL customer satisfaction in 2022?
- Is there a direct influence from operational performance on Central Java (Solo – Yogyakarta) KRL customer loyalty in 2022?
- Is there the direct effect of the quality of services in central java (Solo – Yogyakarta) KRL customer loyalty in 2022?
- Is there a direct influence from KRL customer satisfaction on Central Java (Solo – Yogyakarta) KRL customer loyalty in 2022?
- Is there any indirect effect of operational performance to customer loyalty through Central Java (SoloYogyakarta) KRL customer satisfaction in 2022?
- Is there any indirect effect on the quality of service on customer loyalty through Central Java (Solo-Yogyakarta) KRL customer satisfaction in 2022?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Operational Performance*

Operational performance According to (ratnasari, 2015) is one of the main factors in achieving the goals of a company, The productivity in the company will decrease if the employees perform badly and vice versa. In a company, management has to be able to create a working environment that's conducive and sensitive to the employee conditions in the company in order to create the expected performance. The performance of the employees is an absolute thing that has to be improved in a company in order to achieve the goals that have been set together.

In line with what was stated by (Markos and Sridevi, 2010), employee performance affects company goals. "Employee performance signifies the level of efficiency and Individual productivity that leads to the accomplishment of organization's goals as a result of their positive contributions that ultimately result in the overall organization's performance". Operational performance is the process conformity and performance evaluation of the company's internal operations that can be measured in several elements. Recognise failures, inefficiencies in the work process, and possible abuse of employee authority. Operational performance is a job given to employees to carry out and carry out tasks based on experience and speed, So those

results can be measured because operational performance is generated from multiple dimensions that is, The organization's goal, maintenance of the process, and initiative. Quality is measured by variables of numbers or with certain attributes.

From the above opinions and explanations, it can be synthesized that Operational Performance is the process of achieving predetermined goals in an organisation or company that is influenced by the skills, experience, initiative and motivation of employees and the conditions of the work environment that exist in the company.

B. *Service quality*

According to a journal excerpt (Waluyo, 2018) as a way to assess the effect of customer service quality, you can use the following 5 dimensions that can be measured:

➤ *Physical Evidence (Tangible),*

Capability owned by a company that can show himself to external sides .The physical infrastructure company in contributed to the environment is clear evidence of the services provided by service providers. Physical evidence can be in the form of building, warehouse, equipment, equipment & technology use, looks employee and so on.

➤ *Reliability*

A company ability to deliver services in accordance with what is offered, accurately reliable and guarantee that come into what passes. by consumers Performance has to be in accordance with the wishes of customers , in this same service consistently without any distinction for all customers with a small miscalculation, inflicted timing, service of their customers and sympathetic toward. accurate with accuracy.

➤ *Responsiv*

The ability of the company in providing rapid and precise responsive to customers with little or no fault .And of the required information is also capable of providing customers with clear and accurate .Keeps the customers waiting for is the bad. on the quality of service.

➤ *Guarantee (Assurance)*

A skill owned by the company of knowledge, Experiences and courtesy as well as employee ability to give and grow customer trust to products given by the company. Some components in this matter include communication, The credibility, Security competence and courtesy.

➤ *Empatthy (Empathy)*

The company's ability to give sincere, individual or personal attention specifically given to customers, Such attention by striving to understand and understand consumer desires and expectations. In this case the company must have knowledge, The understanding, The understanding of the customer's needs is precise and clear, so that it can give comfort to customers.

If customers receive services according to their expectations, service quality will be considered good by customers, and conversely, service quality will be considered less good if the service they receive is lower than what customers expected, resulting in customers feeling that their desires and expectations have not been fulfilled. Each organization will be eager to provide effective services so that any job or responsibility given by a customer can go well and properly.

From the opinions and explanations above, It can be synthesized that the quality of service is an act of employment or a service unit in a company that is carried out in full commitment to meet the needs, The wishes and expectations of customers through physical evidence, Reliability, Responsive power, Guarantee and empathy given to customers.

C. Customer satisfaction

The satisfaction of customers can be judged or measured, where perception of the performance of a given product has met the customer's wishes. When assessing customer satisfaction with a product, Can use attributes that form satisfaction.(dukta, 2005) explains that generally consumer satisfaction attributes are:

- The attribute of being associated with the Product
- The attribute of being related to the services
- The attributes of being related to purchasing

The customer's satisfaction is an impression obtained And a feeling of delight or disappoint that appeared after comparison the performance or the outcome of goods and services with previous expectations.(kotler, 2005: 36) on the journal quote (merina et al. , 2016).Factors that can provide customer satisfaction (hendy), 2004: 37) Among other things:

- Product quality, With good quality products, The customer will be satisfied afterwards. Buy and use that product.
- Prices, in general for customers, Cheap prices are a reliable source of satisfaction because of the high value for money that customers will get.
- Service quality, good service quality that is able to provide satisfaction It's generally hard to copy. Service quality is a driver who has many dimensions, One of the popular ones is the quality of service.
- Emotional Factor, the emotional value obtained from a product or service can give customers a sense of satisfaction and pride.
- Ease and Cost, products or services that are easy to access, low cost, can provide comfort, security and efficiency will definitely provide satisfaction to customers.

In increasing customer satisfaction, The company should consider the four dimensions of e-service quality mobile apps, That's the quality of information, The design of the application, The method of payment, As well as security and privacy. The customer's satisfaction can be measured in a

few dimensions that consist of the proportional quality of service, Marketing, And also the price of the product given.

From the opinions and explanations above, it can be synthesized that Customer Satisfaction is a response or assessment from customers regarding the discrepancy between expectations and desires when using a service or product and the reality they feel.

D. Customer loyalty

According to (hasan. et al , 2017) customer loyalty is a pertaining to brand a product , one of them is changing, contract brands in the future the possibility of change, support for a product or probably increase good judgment. of that product

Indicators of customer loyalty refer to research by Purba (2014) which explains that there are several indicators of customer loyalty, namely as follows:

- Recommendation is the consumer's Willingness to recommend products / certain services to colleagues or friends consumers.
- Commitment is the customer's commitment to using e-ticketing in long-standing ties to the industry.
- Repeat purchase, namely the goal of the customer to become a repeat purchaser.

From some opinions and explanations above, It can be synthesized that customer loyalty is a customer's attitude/ behavior in committing commitment to reuse services or previously used products in the future..

III. RESEARCH METHODS

According to (sugiyono , non 2019) probability sample of sampling is the technique does haven't the same opportunities or to each member of the sample. population to be chosen Use sampling techniques non probability sampling (saturated) census method The sample determination technique uses all members of the population to be sampled. The sample technique used was a small sample, if the population count is less than 100 people.

In this research, the number of samples that will be taken is several passengers from Central Java KRL Station (Solo - Yogyakarta) during a field survey at the station and Central Java KRL passengers (Solo - Yogyakarta) as customers of KRL transportation services, namely 80 people, the author took samples from KRL passengers Central Java with consideration of the results in accordance with what happened in the field and relevant. The saturated sample method is a technique for determining the sample if each member of the population will be used as sample.

IV. RESULTS

➤ *Validity Test*

To determine whether a questionnaire can be declared valid or invalid, we need to get the r table first. The formula for the r table is $df = n - 2$. The critical validity limit value used is 0.2199 (for $n=80$). If the calculated r or correlation value is smaller Orless than 0.2199 then the questionnaire item is declared invalid. On the contrary, if the count r value obtained is greater than 0.2199 then the questioner item is the valid.

Below are the results of the validity test of the research instrument (questionnaire) for each research variable:

Table 1. Validity of Test the Results

Pernyataan	Nilai Koefisien Koreksi (r hitung)				Status
	(X1)	(X2)	(Y)	(Z)	
No. 1	0.714	0.707	0.714	0.714	Valid
No. 2	0.709	0.706	0.709	0.709	Valid
No. 3	0.463	0.469	0.463	0.463	Valid
No. 4	0.701	0.698	0.701	0.701	Valid
No. 5	0.881	0.875	0.881	0.881	Valid
No. 6	0.600	0.605	0.600	0.600	Valid

From: The primary data , processed by of statistical package for the social sciences version 25.

Table1 show off that each point from each question on the variables Operational Performance (X1), Service Quality (X2), KRL User Satisfaction (Y)and KRL Customer Loyalty (Z) is declared completely valid.

➤ *Reliability Test*

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Nilai Alpha	Nilai Batas	Status
Kinerja Operasional (X1)	0.764	0.70	Reliable
Kualitas Pelayanan (X2)	0.762	0.70	Reliable
Kepuasan Pengguna KRL (Y)	0.764	0.70	Reliable
Loyalitas Pengguna KRL (Z)	0.764	0.70	Reliable

From: The primary data , processed by of statistical package for the social sciences version 25.

Table2 show off that the overall alpha value of the question items contained in each variable is declared reliable, because the Cronbach Alpha coefficient obtained is greater than 0.70.

Thus, Stated that on the whole the statement from each item variables can be used and distributed to all respondents (80) because each item showing results valid and it is reliable , so as to be done. further analysis.

➤ *The Partial Test*

Table 3. The Partial Test of Structure 1

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.570	2.669		1.713	.091
	KinerjaOperasional	.416	.108	.393	3.836	.000
	KualitasPelayanan	.400	.134	.306	2.981	.004

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Pengguna KRL

From: The primary data , processed by of statistical package for the social sciences version 25

- The Operation performance x1 has an impact on the customer satisfaction of the krl (Y).Showing individual test results (partial) / test t, sig value. 0,000 is smaller than 0.05 or 0,000 0.05, then coefficient analysis of significant lanes. Thus, Operational performance has a positive and significant effect on KRL customer satisfaction. Immediate effect of operational performance on customer satisfaction KRL shown by beta value of 0.393 or 39.3 percent.
- Service Quality (X2)to influences KRL Customer Satisfaction(Y). Showing the individual (partial) test / t test, the Sig value of 0.004 is smaller than 0.05 / [0.001 < 0.05], so the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, Service Quality has a positive and significant influence on KRL Customer Satisfaction. The big influence of Service Quality on KRL Customer Satisfaction is shown by the Beta value of 0.306 / 30.6 %.

Table 4. The Partial Test of Structure 2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.241	1.717		.723	.472
	KinerjaOperasional	.387	.075	.402	5.177	.000
	KualitasPelayanan	.302	.090	.253	3.372	.001
	Kepuasan Pengguna KRL	.330	.072	.363	4.586	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Loyalitas Pengguna KRL

From: The primary data , processed by of statistical package for the social sciences version 25.

- Operational Performance (X1) influences KRL Customer Loyalty (Z). Showing an individual (partial) test or t-test, a Sig value of 0.000 < 0.05 or 0.000 is less than 0.05, Can be stated that the coefficient analysis of the path used is significant. So it can be stated that Operational Performance has a positive and significant influence on KRL Customer Loyalty. The magnitude of the direct influence of Operational Performance on KRL Customer Loyalty is shown by the Beta value obtained, namely 0.402 or 40.2%.
- Service Quality (X2) has an influence on KRL Customer Loyalty (Z). Showing the results of individual (partial) tests or t-tests, a Sig value of 0.000 <0.05 or 0.000 is less than 0.05,Can be stated that the coefficient analysis of the path used is significant. So it can be stated that Service

Quality has a positive and significant influence on KRL Customer Loyalty. The magnitude of the influence of Service Quality on KRL Customer Loyalty is shown by the Beta value obtained, namely 0.253 or 25.3%.

- KRL Customer Satisfaction (Y) has an influence on KRL Customer Loyalty (Z). Showing the results of the individual (partial) test or t-test obtained a Sig value of $0.000 < 0.05$ or 0.000 less than 0.05, Then it can be stated that coefficient track analysis can be significant. So it can be stated that Krl customer satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on Krl customer loyalty. The magnitude of the influence of KRL Customer Satisfaction on KRL Customer Loyalty is shown by the Beta value obtained, namely 0.363 or 36.3%.

➤ *The Sobel Test*

Sobel tests are tests to see if relationships through mediation variables can significantly function as mediators in relationships:

- The mediation of the operational performance of train customer loyalty through train customer satisfaction.

Fig 1 The Sobel test model 1

Based on Fig 1, the one-tailed probability results are $0.00030545 < 0.05$ or 0.00030545 less than 0,05. Thus, it can be conclusion that the KRL Customer Satisfaction variable can mediate the indirect influence of Operational Performance on KRL Customer Loyalty.

- The mediation Testof the Effect of Service Quality on KRL Customer Loyalty through KRL Customer Satisfaction.

Fig 2. The Sobel test model 2

Based on picture2, it see a one-tall probability result of $0.00338959 < 0.05$ or 0.00338959 less than 0,05. Thus, it can be conclusion that of the variable KRL Customer Satisfaction is able to mediate the indirect influence of the Service Quality on KRL Customer Loyalty.

➤ *The Goodness of Fittest Test*

Table 6. The R Square Sub Structure 1

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.597 ^a	.357	.340	1.097
a. Predictors: (Constant), KualitasPelayanan, KinerjaOperasional				

From: The primary data , processed by of statistical package for the social sciences version 25

Table 7.The R Square of Sub Structure 2

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.833 ^a	.694	.682	.692
a. Predictors: (Constant), Kepuasan Pengguna KRL, KualitasPelayanan, KinerjaOperasional				

From: The primary data , processed by of statistical package for the social sciences version 25

Then the total diversity of data that can be explained by the model is measured by:

$$R2m = 1 - (1 - R21) \cdot (1 - R22) \cdot (1 - R2p) \tag{1} R2m$$

$$= 1 - (1 - R21) \cdot (1 - R22) \cdot (1 - R2p) R2m \tag{2}$$

$$= 1 - (0.357) \times (0.694) \tag{3}$$

$$R2m = 0.752$$

The R2mvalue of 0.752 means that the diversity of data known based on the model is 75.20%, While the rest of 24.80 % is described by other variables outside the model. So it can be stated that the research model carried out has a high level of prediction of Behavioral variable dependency marked with coefficient determination values above 50 %.

Fig 3 Path Test the results of diagram

V. THE DISCUSSION

- Operational performance has a positive and significant influence on KRLcustomer satisfaction. According to analysis the coefficient value of operational performance variable path to the cl customer satisfaction variable by 0.393 or 39.3 % with 0 000 significance value. This means it can be concluded that the better operational performance, then KRLcustomer satisfaction will get higher. That way, KRLcustomer satisfaction earned passengers will be increasing.
- Based on the results of the analysis obtained the value the variable quality of services on variables customer satisfaction of 0,306 or 30,6 % 0,004. the significance of This means that it can be concluded that the better the quality of service and customer satisfaction will increase.
- Operational performance has a positive and significant influence on KRLcustomer loyalty. According to analysis the coefficient value of operational performance variable path to the KRLcustomer loyalty variable by 0.402 or 40.30 % with 0 000 significance value. This means it can be concluded that the better operational performance, then the customer's loyalty KRL will get better. That way, KRLcustomers' loyalty will increase more and more.
- Service Quality has a positive and significant influence on KRL Customer Loyalty. Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that the path coefficient value of the Service Quality variable for the KRL Customer Loyalty variable was 0.306 or 30.6% with a significance value of 0.004. This means that it can be concluded that the better the service quality, the better KRL customer loyalty will be. In this way, KRL Customer Loyalty will increase.
- KRLCustomer satisfaction will make a positive and significant to train customer loyalty based on the results of the analysis obtained variable customer satisfaction rail

against variable customer loyalty by 36,3 % 0,363 or train with. 0,000 significance This means that it can be concluded that the better customer satisfaction and customer loyalty will be better.

- KRL Customer satisfaction can mediate the operational performance of customer loyalty. Train This means that It can be conclusion that customer satisfaction corresponds to the operational performance applied, train can increase customer loyalty and customer satisfaction is intervening as variable intermediate or variable that serves to strengthen the operational performance of customer loyalty.
- KRL User Satisfaction is able to function as a mediator or mediate the influence of Service Quality on KRL User Loyalty. This means to conclude that the satisfaction of the client krl that corresponds to the quality of service given is able to increase the loyalty of the client krl so that the satisfaction of the client as an intervening variable or variable intermediate proves to be functioning in strengthening the effectly of service quality of the client's KRL loyalty.

VI. THE CONCLUSION

- The Operational performance and have a positive influence significantly to train customer satisfaction.
- The quality of services have a positive influence on customer satisfaction and significant train.
- The Operational Performance have a positive & significant influence on KRL CustomerLoyalty.
- The Service Quality have a positive & significant influence on KRL Customer Loyalty.
- KRL Customer satisfaction and have a positive influence significantly to train. customer loyalty
- KRL Customer Satisfaction is the able to mediate the indirect influence of the Operational Performance on KRL CustomerLoyalty.
- KRLCustomer Satisfactions able to mediate the indirect influence of the Service Quality on KRL Customer Loyalty.

VII. THE RECOMMENDATIONS

- To increasing & maintain KRL customer loyalty& to avoid a decline in Central Java (Solo - Yogyakarta) KRL users or passengers resulting from passenger dissatisfaction which results in not reusing Central Java (Solo - Yogyakarta) KRLservices, it's necessary to improve for the operational performance and service quality to increase KRL Customer Satisfaction. This can lead to increased KRL customer loyalty as service users.
- Researchers were going, conducted research on operational performance , service quality customer satisfaction and loyalty customers will train variabel-variabel suggested toexamine other also have significant influence. So it's hope that these studies can be useful in providing input and recommendations to Central Java (Solo - Yogyakarta) KRL operators & the academic of world.

VIII. IMPLICATIONS

Based on conclusions from the results of research and recommendation proposed writer disassemble, above but its implications are operational performance and quality of service for customer satisfaction is the better, the provision of services is in conformity with expectation, customers operational activities can work optimal and consistent with the objectives of the company guided by standard operating company, so the use of technology to facilitate easier access online services customers in. With operational performance and service quality, better hence any problems that arise will soon there is a solution to avoid disloyalty passengers to use the services back.

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